

English Abbreviations

Uniform Abbreviations:

"er" loop abbreviation

hook diacritic = ̉

This symbol resembles the certain variations of the medieval Latin abbreviation for "er/ar/re." In our manuscripts, it mainly stands in for "er," though occasionally takes on other meanings (noted below. For a discussion of its Latin counterpart, See Capelli pp. 19-29, specifically sections 4.3-4.35.

Manuscript Image	Character	Notes
	ḋ	
	ė	
	ġ	
	ṁ Ṁ	also <i>ir</i>
	ṅ	
	ṗ	also <i>re</i>
	ṙ	mainly just <i>e</i>
	ṡ	
	ṫ	
	ḃ	

Manuscript Image	Character	Notes
	ú	
	v̇	
	ÿ	

▷ "ri" small 2-shaped abbreviation

zig zag diacritic = ͛

This symbol most closely resembles the Latin 2-shaped abbreviation, often used for *u* or *a* (see Capelli pages 29-30, section 4.4-4.41). However in our manuscripts it almost always stands for "ri."

Manuscript Image	Character	Notes
	ř	
missing image?	ř̇	
	ṗ	
	ṫ	also ir or er

▷ "ra" upward facing wavy line

diaeresis diacritic = ̈

This symbol closely resembles the Latin "r/re/ra/ar" wavy line abbreviation. As Capelli notes, in the 14th and 15th century this symbol develops into a broken bar or two dots closely spaced, and we see a similar ball-type form in some instances below (see Capelli pp. 13-16, specifically sections 3.4-3.42). Given limited wavy-line options in Unicode, we have chosen to represent the abbreviation by its late form, with two balls.

Manuscript Image	Character
	ġ
	ṅ

Manuscript Image	Character
	p̃
	ü

▷ "ur" downward facing wavy line

tilde diacritic = ̃

This symbol most closely resembles a version of the Latin "ur/tur/er" abbreviation, which Capelli describes as a "2" or "S" on its side (see Capelli pp.13-117, 3.5). In our English manuscripts, this symbol looks more like an inversion of the "ra" symbol (above) than a "2" or "S." We have chosen to represent this abbreviation with a tilde, which is closest to its form.

Manuscript Image	Character
	ẽ
	õ
	t̃

▷ "n/m" macron

macron = ̄

In most, the macron is used, as in Latin, to represent a missing "m" or "n." In some cases, it represents "u" (for example when placed over an "n").

Manuscript Image	Character
	ē
	m̄
	ō
	n̄

Manuscript Image	Character
	ū
	ȳ

Discrete Abbreviations

Manuscript Image	Description	Meaning	Character	Unicode
	d with downstroke	is (e.g. <i>dis</i>) or e (e.g. <i>de</i>)	ꝿ	ɖ
	h with cross stroke	et (e.g. <i>het</i>)	ꝥ	ħ
	e with small stroke	m or n (e.g. <i>em</i>)	e'	eʼ
	g with dot	ro (<i>gro</i>)	g°	g˚
	l with cross stroke	ett (e.g. <i>lett</i>) or is (e.g. <i>lis</i>) or e (e.g. <i>el</i> or <i>le</i>)	†	ꝉ
	welsh l	e (e.g. <i>lle</i>)	ll	ỻ
	p with stroke through descender	er or ar (e.g. <i>per</i> or <i>par</i>)	p and ꝑ	ꝑ Ꝑ
	p with loop on descender	ro (e.g. <i>pro</i>)	ꝑ	ꝓ
	thorn with u diacritic	pou	þ̥	þͧ
	w with t suprascript	with	ŵ	wͭ

Latin Abbreviations

Manuscript Image	Description	Meaning	Character	Unicode
	a with dot	?	a°	a˚
	c with macron	an - t (e.g. <i>anct</i>)	c̄	c̄
	d with shoulder	audi (e.g. <i>dauid</i>)	d'	dʾ
	d with vertical line	um (e.g. <i>dum</i>)	?	?
	h with dot	hoc	h°	h̊
missing image?	h with comma?	es (i.e. <i>Ihesu</i>)	h'	h̉
	macron i	mn (e.g. <i>mni</i>)	ī	ī
	p with tilde	ur (e.g. <i>pur</i>)	p̃	p̃
	t with 2-shaped tilde	ur (e.g. <i>tur</i>)	t̂	t̃
missing image?	t with macron	us (e.g. <i>tus</i>)	t̄	t̄
	character resembling 9	con	9	ꝯ
	character resembling 4 or y with strike through	rum	ȳ	ɏ
	character resembling 3	us (e.g. <i>bus</i>)	3	ꝫ

Manuscript Image	Description	Meaning	Character	Unicode
	q plus d with endstroke	quod	qd	qdɖ
	q with right hook	quod	q̄	ꝙ
	tironian et	and	7	⁊
	tironian et + c with left hook	et cetera	7c̄	7c̉

Additional Abbreviations

Manuscript Image	Description	Meaning	Character
	paragraph marker	new paragraph	¶
	vertical bar	divides cramped words	
missing image?	punctus elevatus (looks like inverted semi-colon)	pause	⸘